

Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) Complexes of 3, 4,5-Trimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetic acid

NITYANANDA SAHA* AND D. BHATTACHARYYA

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Laboratories, University College of Science ;
92, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Calcutta-700 009.

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Solid complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with 3, 4, 5-Trimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetic acid (synthesised for the first time) [TPzAH] have been isolated both in the hydrated and anhydrous states and characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, molar conductances, magnetic susceptibilities, electronic and vibrational spectral data. The hydrated complexes $M(\text{TPzA})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been assigned distorted octahedral configuration ; the spectral bands of violet $\text{Cu}(\text{TPzA})_2$ are in accord with D_{4h} symmetry. The anhydrous complexes are in general, probably polymeric, the acetato group being bidentate and bridging as evident from i. r. data.

THE coordination chemistry of pyrazole derived ligands because of their potential medicinal and biological importance¹ has received much attention during recent years². We like to report here, the synthesis of a, hitherto unreported, tetra-substituted pyrazole, viz. 3, 4, 5-Trimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetic acid (I) (herein after abbreviated as TPzAH) and non electrolytic bis-complexes of (I) with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II), both in hydrated and anhydrous forms, characterised by elemental analyses, molar conductances, magnetic data, electronic and vibrational spectral studies.

Fig 1

Experimental

a) Preparation of the ligand :

3, 4, 5-Trimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetic acid was prepared from the reaction of 3, 4, 5-Trimethyl Pyrazole³ and ethyl bromoacetate (E. Merck, Germany) followed by saponification with NaOH of the corresponding ethyl ester, b.p. 102°-105° (8mm of Hg) following a method very similar to that adopted by Habraken et al⁴. The acid on recrystallisation from ethanol gave shining white flakes, m.p. 191°.

(Anal. Found ; C, 57.30 ; H, 7.05 ; N, 16.75%
Calcd. C₈H₁₃N₂O₂ ; C, 57.11 ; H, 7.19 ; N, 16.66%

b) Preparation of the complexes

An aqueous alcoholic solution of the ligand (0.01 mole) was mixed with hydrated metal chloride or acetate (0.305 mole) dissolved in minimum volume of the same solvent. The resulting solution was adjusted to pH 6 by the dropwise addition of dilute ammonia. The blue Cu(II) complex precipitated out immediately, while the Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes took several hours (5-6 hours) to crystallise out. In each case, the microcrystalline coloured complex, thus separated, was filtered, washed well with ethanol and then dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl₂.

Cu(TPzA)₂ :

Copper chloride dihydrate (0.005 mole) dissolved

*For correspondence.

in alcohol (30ml) was added to an alcoholic solution (30 ml) of the ligand (0.01 mole); the resulting solution after being adjusted to a pH 4~5 (with ammonia) was kept on water bath; and the violet compound separated within 30 minutes was collected as above.

$M(TPzA)_2$ ($M=Ni, Co$):

The hydrated complex in each case was heated in an oven at $(135 \pm 5)^\circ$ for 3 to 4 hours, when the anhydrous compound was obtained often accompanied by change of colour.

c) Physical measurements

Electronic spectra in purified analar grade solvents were recorded in Hungarian Spectromom

soluble in common organic solvents except the violet $Cu(TPzA)_2$ which normally remains insoluble in innocent organic solvents at room temperature. The molar conductance values of the complexes in methanol solution [except the violet $Cu(TPzA)_2$] indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

All the complexes are magnetically normal high spin ones; the moments of $Co(II)$ complexes are above the spin only value of 3.89 B.M. for high spin octahedral complexes, due to a high orbital contribution⁵.

Copper (II) complexes:

The electronic spectrum of the blue $Cu(TPzA)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ shows in methanol solution a broad asymmetric

Table—1

Formulae, analytical data, magnetic moments and the molar conductances of the metal complexes of 3, 4, 5-Trimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetic acid

Complex	Colour	Found%		Calculated%		μ_{eff} (B.M.) at 299°K	Molar conductance λ_m (mole ⁻¹ cm ² ohm ⁻¹) in 1 x 10 ⁻³ M methanol solution at 30°
		Metal	N	Metal	N		
1. $[Cu(TPzA)_2 \cdot (H_2O)_2]$	Blue	14.72	12.80	14.64	12.91	2.19	8.73
2. $Cu(TPzA)_2$	Violet	15.95	14.20	15.97	14.08	1.88	—
3. $[Ni(TPzA)_2 \cdot (H_2O)_2]$	Bluish green	13.59	13.20	13.68	13.05	3.15	9.41
4. $Ni(TPzA)_2$	Pale green	15.00	14.19	14.94	14.25	3.17	9.06
5. $[Co(TPzA)_2 \cdot (H_2O)_2] \cdot H_2O$	Light pink	13.14	12.48	13.17	12.52	4.89	11.13
6. $Co(TPzA)_2$	Violet	15.07	14.27	14.98	14.24	4.98	9.85

TPzAH = a molecule of 3, 4, 5-Trimethyl Pyrazole-1-acetic acid.

Table—2

Electronic Absorption spectra of $M(TPzA)_2$ complexes

Complex	State	$\lambda_{max}(cm^{-1})$	(ϵ molar for solutions)
1. $[Cu(TPzA)_2 \cdot (H_2O)_2]$ (blue)	soln.*	14,285 (73.18) br	
2. $Cu(TPzA)_2$ (violet)	Reflectance	15,400 sh; 18,200 br	
	Soln. a)	14,590 br	
	Soln. b)	16,130 wsh; 14,920(101.2) br.	
3. $[Ni(TPzA)_2 \cdot (H_2O)_2]$ (bluish green)	Soln.*	9,710(6.56); 13,160sh; 15,270(5.38); 25,970(12.72)	
4. $Ni(TPzA)_2$ (Pale green)	Soln.*	9,800(7.64); 13,330sh; 15,380(6.09); 25,970(14.44)	
5. $[Co(TPzA)_2 \cdot (H_2O)_2] \cdot H_2O$ (light pink)	Soln.*	9,010(4.78); 10,530wsh; 15,880sh; 19,610(14.24)	
6. $Co(TPzA)_2$ (violet)	Soln.*	9,170(4.97); 10,000sh; 19,800(15.66); 20,400sh	

br = broad; sh = shoulder; wsh = weak shoulder

a) in methanol containing few drops of water (heating for 5 mins. over water bath)

b) in pyridine.

* in dried redistilled analar grade methanol at 25° - 30°

'201' spectrophotometer and the reflectance spectrum of the $Cu(TPzA)_2$ was taken in a Zeiss PMQ II spectrophotometer with a reflectance attachment RA3 (at the University of N.S.W., Australia). Magnetic susceptibilities were measured in a Gouy balance using G. R. $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as calibrant. Electrolytic conductances were determined using a Philips PR 9500 type conductivity bridge. The infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in a Beckman 20 IR spectrophotometer using KBr plates.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and other pertinent data of the complexes have been compiled in Table 1, while the electronic spectral data are placed in Table 2.

The complexes are insoluble in water, but are

band centred around $14,300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting an usual distorted octahedral stereochemistry with a symmetry lower than O_h .

The reflectance spectrum of the violet $Cu(TPzA)_2$ is characterised by a main broad band at $18,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (with considerable asymmetry on the low energy side) and a well defined shoulder near $15,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which may be assigned to ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_1 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ transitions respectively in D_4h symmetry^{7,8,9}. This complex

goes into solution fairly in hot methanol with time (~5-6 hours) yielding a blue solution which gives a nearly identical absorption spectrum (a broad band at ~14,700 cm^{-1}) with that of blue $Cu(TPzA)_2 \cdot$

2H₂O. In strong coordinating solvents like pyridine, the complex gives a blue solution where the absorption peak is shifted to lower frequency (~14,900cm⁻¹) compared to that of the solid state spectrum suggesting a change in stereochemistry of the complex species in solution of the solvent. The violet Cu(TPzA)₂ thus probably belongs to a tetragonal geometry in the solid state and in methanol or more particularly in pyridine, solvated penta or hexa-coordinated species are produced^{10, 11, 12}.

Nickel (II) complexes :

Similar electronic spectral data (probably due to solvation) of Ni(TPzA)₂, both hydrated and anhydrous varieties in methanol (Table 2) are typical of distorted 6-coordinate Ni(II) ; three principal bands near 9,700cm⁻¹, 15,300cm⁻¹ and 26,000cm⁻¹ are readily attributable to ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions respectively in O_h symmetry. The low molar extinction values of the spectral bands (Table 2) and the corresponding ν_2/ν_1 ratio (≈ 1.56) for both the varieties of present Ni(II) complexes give additional support of a pseudooctahedral environment^{13,14} in these complexes. The weak bands at ~13,300cm⁻¹ occurring as shoulders are probably due to spin forbidden ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ (D) transitions.^{15, 16}

Cobalt (II) complexes :

The hydrated Cobalt (II) complex, when subjected to thermal treatment in a thermo balance (local design ; heating rate 7°C/min.), loses one molecule water at 90°, while the rest two molecules of water are eliminated only at 140° giving the corresponding anhydrous species ; thus a reasonable formulation of the hydrated species would be [Co(TPzA)₂(H₂O)₂].H₂O. The absorption spectra of both hydrated and anhydrous Co(TPzA)₂, in methanol resemble those of an octahedral Co(II) complex (Table 2) and the main bands at ca. 9000cm⁻¹ and 19,600cm⁻¹ may be

assigned to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(P)(\nu_2)$ respectively and the two shoulders (Table 2) to the spin-forbidden or two electron transitions¹⁷.

I. R. Spectra

Although direct i.r. evidence for M-N bonding could not be presented here due to the limited range of spectrophotometer used, nevertheless the x-ray crystallography has definitely established the pyridine N-atom of the pyrazole ring to become an obvious point of attachment to metal ions in pyrazole metal complexes^{18, 19, 20}.

The I. R. spectrum of TPzAH molecule shows two intense bands at 1710cm⁻¹ and 1410cm⁻¹ which have been assigned as the symmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the OCO⁻ group²¹. In the metal complexes, the asymmetric OCO⁻ vibration has in general, been shifted to much lower frequency side (1600cm⁻¹) confirming the participation of the carboxyl group in complex formation.

The broad band at 3540-3530cm⁻¹ and a medium sharp band around 900cm⁻¹ in all hydrated complexes indicate the coordinated nature of water molecules²². These bands are, however, absent in the anhydrous complexes.

The greater Δ values (vide Table 3) for the hydrated compounds than for the anhydrous ones may be ascribed²³ to the fact that as the covalent character of the M—O bond increases [structure (B)], the carboxyl group becomes more asymmetrical resulting in an increase in Δ values, compared to that of the free ion [structure (A)]. As the strength of the O→M bond increases [structure (C)] so does the symmetry of the CO₂⁻ group and thus a decrease in Δ results.

Table-3

Compound	Carboxyl stretching frequencies (cm ⁻¹) of the ligand and M(TPzA) ₂ in I.R. Spectra.		
	$\nu_{\text{OCO}_2^-}$, asym.	$\nu_{\text{OCO}_2^-}$ sym.	ν_{CO_2} asym - ν_{CO_2} sym = Δ
TPzAH*	1710S	1410ms	300
[Cu(TPzA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1605S	1400S	205
Cu(TPzA) ₂	1610S	1415ms	195
[Ni(TPzA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	1605S	1390ms	215
Ni(TPzA) ₂	1610bs	1400s	210
[Co(TPzA) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O	1610bs	1400s	210
Co(TPzA) ₂	1600bs	1400s	200

s = sharp : ms = medium sharp : bs = broad sharp
* anhydrous solid.

Thus, in the hydrated complexes $[M(\text{TPzA})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, the ligand behaves as a bidentate one, the carboxyl group functioning as in (B) whereas in the anhydrous $M(\text{TPzA})_2$ compounds, the ligand functions as a terdentate one having bridging carboxylato group [structure (C)].

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